

Comparison of Glucose in Urine with Likening of Pigeons as Pets

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ABSTRACT

If someone is liking pigeons as pets, this may be due to their intelligent, effortless, and loving nature. The chief objectives of this study were to relate pigeon lovers as a pet with the level of glucose in their urine. Around 100 students of Bahauddin Zakariya University Multan Pakistan were participants of this study. Pee has glucose that is measured for measuring the glucose in urine. If glucose is not present in the urine it shows the kidney is working well. There is no major effect of glucose in urine with the love of a pigeon as a pet.

Keywords: Glucose test, Glucose in the urine, Students.

INTRODUCTION

The quantity of glucose present in urine is known as urine glucose. If we observed that sugar is not present that shows that our kidney is working well. During the body's functioning sugar is absorbed through the kidney. The person has a problem with its functioning if a small amount of glucose is present in the urine.

Disease caused if glucose is small or higher quantity present is known as glucosuria. The main cause of the disease is diabetes from glucosuria. Between 0 to 0.8 mmol/L is the normal amount of glucose in the urine. Glucose level is also measured by urine by urine glucose test.

The most beautiful bird that is used to domesticated in houses is the pigeon. These birds are also found in the wild region. In the old era, messages are conveyed through these birds. These birds are most loved by the kings of this era. Meat is also taken from these birds which is beneficial for some diseases and winter seasons. Some of these birds fight with each other in a competition to see which pigeon is the most powerful. In the exhibitions in some countries, these birds have used which bird is the most beautiful. If someone is liking pigeons as pets may be due to their intelligent, effortless, and loving nature.

The purpose of this study was to link urine glucose with pigeon loving as a pet [1-4].

Methods and Materials

100 students joined this study and they were university student with age 19-20.

Measurement of Urine in Glucose

Urine glucose is measured in the conditions of glucose in their urine. They have to pee and fill their compartment at a special point through which we get the unnecessary bit holders. Urinalysis is the test that is performed to measure the amount of glucose in the urine.

Study Design

Questionnaire-based work where mood correlates with the pigeon lover and sugar level present in the urine.

Statistical Analysis

The experimental works were performed on MS excel.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The percentage of this work with the sugar in the urine is given below in the table.

The subjects that took part in this work are the aggregate of 100 that were undertaking esteem. This discussion shows the average of the subjects that were interested or not in likening of pigeons with the level of sugar in the urine. 82 girls and 18 boys were working on this project.

About 10.44% of subjects were pigeon-loving while 89.66% were not pigeon lovers. The subjects that were normally had sugar in their urine were not pigeon lovers while glucose levels present in the urine of those who were affectionate with pigeons.

- A glucose in the urine is a test used to measure glucose amount in urine and may be part of urinalysis (used to check general health).
- It is the type of sugar, the main source of energy and carries to cells by the blood.
- Glucose is present in a small amount normally.
- If glucose is high in the blood, then it may be a sign of diabetes.
- For In high glucose levels, the doctor will order a blood glucose test to help with treatment.
- Urine glucose tests are not accurate as blood glucose tests, blood glucose tests are mostly used for diabetes treatment.
- But blood glucose test is difficult in case of small veins, repeated punctures, and fear of needles.
- The symptoms of diabetes include increased thirst, urination, hunger, fatigue, blurred vision, numbness on hands or feet, unhealed sores, and unreasoned weight loss.
- In pregnancy, glucose in the urine is common but high glucose can cause gestational diabetes.
- Gestational diabetes can be managed by proper diet and regular exercise with proper medication of glucose tests and insulin.
- The normal glucose level in urine is 0-0.8 mmol/L.
- Genetic mutation, pregnancy, and some medical conditions can cause high glucose in urine.
- Some persons don't show any symptoms with high glucose levels in urine.
- High glucose levels in urine can be treated by reducing intake of sugar, carbohydrates, smoking, alcohol, and processed food, loss of weight, drinking plenty of water, and regular healthy physical exercises with proper medication prescribed by the doctor.

Table 1. Relation of pigeon lover with glucose in the urine

Total subjects=100		Likeness		Dis-likeness	
Male	Female	Urine glucose present	Urine glucose absent	Urine glucose present	Urine glucose absent
18	82	10.44	89.66	15.77	84.23

Questionnaire-based work gave important results in this study.

The question-based study is very helpful for students for making them confident in their study and research work.

CONCLUSION

It was observed from this study that the subjects with higher or lower sugar levels in the urine did not affect the likening or disliking of pigeons as pets.

Declarations

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Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare no competing financial, professional and personal interests.

Consent for publication

Authors declare that they consented for the publication of this research work.

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